

ESL Teachers' Barriers To Use Activities In Classroom: A Study From ESL Teachers' Perspective

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: January 31, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Use of Activity, Teachers' Constraints, ESL classroom, Learning Outcomes</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5940809</p>	<p><i>The paper aims to report the factors affecting the utilization of activities in ESL classroom to enhance ESL learning of Elementary Level Students in Government schools. In particular, the study attempts to explore why ESL Teachers do not make use of activities in ESL classroom and what are their perceptions regarding the constraints in the way of utilizing activities in the classrooms. For this purpose, data were collected through specially-tailored questionnaire and semi - structured interviews. To ensure authenticity and to provide more reliable results, quantitative data were supported by qualitative data and opinions of 100 participants were taken and analyzed through Likert scale. Convenient Sampling Technique was used to gather data by means of questionnaire and Cronbach's alpha () technique was utilized to authenticate the reliability and internal consistency of the questionnaire. The participants' feedback further led the researcher to probe deep into the participants' understanding of as to why the ESL teachers in state-run institutions do not utilize activities in ESL classroom to enhance learning. It is obvious from the findings that if certain constraints are properly dealt with, the use of activity in ESL classroom can be made possible which may eventually help enhance learning and achieve learning outcomes at school level.</i></p>

Introduction

In academic domain, teaching methodology has always been a much debatable issue and a plethora of research is available on this. This is because the students' learning outcome is directly proportional to teachers' teaching techniques and methodologies that he/she utilizes in the class while teaching. Related to this notion, the teachers, their skill and competency in teaching have a deep effect on students' learning and counts much in achieving expected learning outcomes. The teacher plays the pivotal role in this context and he must be able to change his methodology according to various needs of the hour and should be able to consider criteria after taking into account current academic needs and demands. Erickson (1978) argues that "Effective learning in the classroom depends on the teacher's ability to maintain the interest that brings students to the course in the first place."

The paper probes into the demand and utility of activities in the language class to make ESL learning more interesting, long-lasting, productive and result-oriented in today's educational realm. The research also brings to forefront the constraints and hurdles that ESL teachers usually face to utilize activity-based teaching method. The research also offers suggestions on how to overcome these constraints positively to improve students' academic output and finally ensuring academic excellence.

Activity Based Learning (ABL) is not a completely new style of teaching. It can be traced back at least as far as Socrates and Humboldt. It can well be called a setup where students actively and individually take active part in the learning experience, and do not mere sit as lazy learners or back-benchers, resting their back against the walls. Activity Based English Language Teaching is a method which the ESL practitioners use to focus on active involvement of students in learning the TL. Through this method, students are put in a situation where they learn the TL with the help of different activities. In this activity- based method of teaching, the teacher teaches by making the learners rigorously participate in some specially tailored purposeful activity. David (2007) emphasizes that activity based teaching method inculcates the element of joy, fellowship by giving value to each other's opinions. This method lessens the element of ambiguity in learners' understanding of concepts. Similarly, Sharma (2010), on the importance of activity in teaching, argues that the use of activity enhances learners' autonomy of learning. It also provides assistance and paves way for learners to develop a positive learning aptitude which the students usually gain in the end. Activity-based learning ensures easy-to-go tasks. The learners feel much more encouraged, motivated, active, lively, ready, and exhibit the very skills in dealing other matters in life. Learning by doing is real learning that provides the learners with sensory experience. In learning through activity, the teachers play the role of guide also, to direct the students on how to learn by taking part in activity. As this method focuses on creative aspect of learning and experience, the students feel motivated and willing to learn, that finally helps them comprehend concepts and develop critical thinking. As this method

enhances students' stimulus for learning, they feel inclined to be a part of learning process by taking part in different activities specifically tailored by the EFL teachers for educational purpose. This is what Shah & Rahat (2014), assert confidently that this method gives learners a right place to think over their academic problems and find out solutions to those by calling their own receptive and creative skill.

Language teaching embedded with activities let the students enjoy a totally new and true learning environment. It paves way for both independent and group learning. This method helps young learners overcome shyness in the class and develops a spirit of leadership. It strengthens learners' autonomy and element of initiation as positive outcomes of learning. It also emphasizes critical thinking by deeply understanding of the subject under study. It enhances students' desire to learn and does not let them get board, as every student remains active throughout the activity whether it is a pair work or group work. It helps the learners develop a healthy competition among them and encourages interaction among them (Bhatti, 2020). The research, however, is strongly meant to observe teachers' attitudes towards imparting significance to activities in classroom teaching and find out the constraints that stand as hurdles in their way to utilize activities during teaching in ESL classroom.

Explicitly, this paper attempted to address the following two propositions:

1. An investigation of ESL teachers' attitude to employ activities in ESL classroom to enhance learning.
2. The prevailing constraints and hurdles to use activities in ESL classroom for elementary level students.

2. Statement of the problem.

The present scenario of teaching target language to ESL learners in our public schools is very pathetic. Teachers are relying on much older and clichéd methods of teaching language that forcibly and unnaturally force the students for rote learning and cramming. As a result, the teachers do not achieve the expected results, learning outcomes. Language teachers are still following the ages-old methods and techniques of teaching language, which has made the whole learning process monotonous and discouraging for the students. Following the same clichéd method of teaching, the creative and functional aspects of teaching language are often ignored and the students tend to rely on rote learning as the only thing to resort to. Cramming and rote-learning by students finally result in failure of the whole learning process, thus depriving the students to produce desired results. They remain passive throughout the class and remain unable to grasp the language being taught and, resultantly, feel discouraged, demotivated to learn and even neglected. Different factors like lack of motivation, irrelevant resources, absence or insufficient teaching kits, disorganized classrooms, unwillingness and tardiness on the part of teachers, insufficient duration of class period, crowded classes, lack of lingual exposure and many other similar problems do not let the teachers re-concentrate, reconsider and revamp their old method of teaching language in the class. The teachers remain unable to utilize activities in the language class to make their teaching productive, creative and result-oriented, with far better learning outcomes. Considering the need of inculcating modern pedagogy in present educational scenario, the study addresses in detail all these constraints on the way and reveals the importance of the need of paradigm shift in pedagogical domain. The research done so far only focuses on the significance and utility of activities in teaching at various levels, without addressing and reconsidering as to how to tackle the possible constraints and hurdles in the way of language teachers to utilize this method successfully. The present research bridges the gulf and throws light not only on the teachers' perceptions on the matter under focus, but also offers ways and means on how to deal successfully with the possible constraints that do not let the ESL teachers employ activities during teaching to elementary school students.

3. Literature Review.

Teaching is believed to be a highly arduous and demanding job across the globe. It is generally because of the crucial role the language teachers play in teaching profession. This is why teachers in every country are believed to be the foundation stone of students' academic carrier and the accomplishment of the whole education system in a country. Teachers play a pivotal role in educating the students at every level by utilizing a variety of innovative techniques and methods to impart knowledge to students and achieving Students Learning Outcomes (SLOs). They are like bright lamps that spread rays of knowledge to enlighten students' minds and help them in achieving academic excellence by using and improving their teaching skills. Shedding light on this proposition, Naibaho (2019) says that teaching requires "a lot of responsibility and that responsibility is not an easy responsibility to do". He further argues that a teacher undergoes through different roles to make the students understand the topic he or she is going to teach and to ensure conceptual clarity. A teacher is an actor and reformer, a gardener and a watchman, who not only takes care of his seeds but also looks after them till they are grown up plants. During this process, he reflects again and again and devises various techniques to bring the seed up.

Teaching and learning are the two wheels of the same cart, where one wheel is useless without the other (Anwar, 2019). He further argues that use of activities in teaching improves students' motivation to learn and their reflective skills. Task-based method of teaching may be taken as an approach towards ESL teaching, where different and specially- tailored activities are utilized to ensure the best natural environment (Suydam & Higgins, 1977). Teaching which requires a task to be completed by students is such a pedagogical technique

employed by ESL practitioners where learners are offered to play active role in the whole learning process, thereby attaining learning outcomes. As the focus is on the learner, the learner is sure to take full part in learning. So, the part of the teacher that he or she plays in this scenario is all the more important, as he sits on the back foot and organizes the learning activity. Whereas, the case is totally otherwise in traditional teaching, in which the more focus is generally on memorizing grammatical rules, vocabulary and cramming Urdu translations of the prescribed texts only.

Figure 1. A glance of the conventional method of teaching Present Continuous Tense.

Set with comparison to the old and conventional way of teaching, ABL specifically focuses on conceptual learning, for it has been a fact universally acknowledged that if learners call upon and utilize more than one sense, the learner retains information for much longer time. Shah & Rahat (2014) go on to argue that if a learner is put in a particular situation in which he or she has to think on by calling his or her senses, learning becomes easy and productive in the sense that it has lasting effects on memory. Bahar and Aksut (2020) further point out that if children learn by doing some activity, they can develop a sense of inquisitiveness. They further stress that it is indispensable to provide such exposure in which children can think upon by their own and create various ideas autonomously. According to this pool of thinkers, ABL keeps the participators engaged by providing them with both learning and real-life experiences simultaneously. Yangin & Dindar (2007) bring to highlight another important point, asserting that mostly teachers choose old and conventional method because they don't have any resources to use on their disposal and, this may be one of the reasons as to why most of our teachers largely depend on lecture method. They don't feel the need of using any activity to make their teacher more creative, joyful and productive, and as a result, learners remain unable to actively participate in the whole learning process. They remain lazy till the whole duration of the class and ultimately do not achieve what is called conceptual clarity, and feel themselves compelled to rote learning. This approach to learning develops such minds of learners in which they gradually feel themselves neglected and remain unable to ensure the creative aspects of learning, as they do not find a situation to employ their own critical thinking skill. Shah & Rahat (2014) on the other hand, very well argue that teaching approach that entertains the use of activities do not let the student become passive and sluggish throughout the lesson, and this helps achieve student learning outcomes to a great extent. A well-defined language learning method should be embedded with activities and it paves way for learning a language (Hansraj, 2017).

A teaching method, however, can entertain numerous activities to make learning interesting and productive. The use of activities make learning fruitful and creative, as these activities make the learners think by their own and create by their own in certain situations. A child does not achieve expertise in swimming until he is put in that situation, similarly, a student cannot learn until he or she is put in the right exposure where he or she can think or reflect creatively (Rillero, 1994). Similarly, Ibatova (2019) points out that learners should practice by their own if they want to learn something. Considering current pedagogical practices, Shah and

Rahat (2014) assert that the concept of ESL learning in Pakistan is pathetic and needs to undergo a complete change to cope with the changing pedagogical demands.

In ABL, a teacher has more than one additional role to perform. He is a teacher and a facilitator one and the same time. He may assign different roles to students also and observes them keenly during the session. In this regard, Hansraj (2017) argues that the teacher acts as helper to learners. The actual practicality of this method, Suydam & Higgins (1977) expound, is not only to make the learning environment convivial but also lessen the stress and authority of the teacher. The same proposition is logically supported by Weimer (2002) who asserts that in this method of teaching, the term “learner-centered” or “learning-centered” remains dominant over other theories. In this method students remain engaged in activity during learning and actively participate in the whole learning process excitedly, as they come across different tasks assigned to them by the teacher who is supposed to instruct and observe them during session. This is totally a new concept of teaching which does not leave the teacher passive by simply delivering the lesson or sharing some information before the students and that all form his side and expecting the students to cram all the stuff being taught to them and vomit out when required. In this setup, learners were invariably thought of like something to receive information, without any sense of comprehension on their part (Hansraj, 2017, p.4435). The teaching with the help of activity appeals students’ hidden and dormant faculties and makes them critical thinkers (Fuad, Akbar & Zubo, 2018). Moreover, Zaripova (2020) is very much true when he says, “it does not let the learner get bored.”

Illeris (2000) further expounds his proposition. He asserts that this method takes into account other related areas associated with students’ cognitive domains like students’ psychological and emotional development that are part of learning process. Cahyati, S. S., Parmawati, A., & Atmawidjaja (2019), on the importance of the use of activity in the ESL classroom, argue that the selection of productive and suitable materials for learners is important part of teaching-learning process, as it makes the whole learning process more life-like, result-oriented and meaningful. By adding activity during teaching in ESL classroom, students, says Garner (1987), can connect the present learning with the past experiences and try to grab the new topic by their own. He argues that this method of learning enhances students’ skill of perceiving things (information in this case) more clearly and logically. This ensures autonomy which itself is a great achievement on the part of the teachers. Long (1990), in this context, asserts that this uncontrolled study develops behavioral activities, which further focus on gathering and absorbing threads of information. Long further argues that the students feel more motivated to set objectives to be achieved and efforts required, thus resulting in being individual agents for learning. Kugamoorthy, S. (2012) asserts that ABL is much more useful in the streamlining cognitive skills of students. Keeping in mind the importance of Bloom’s taxonomy, this method, being a natural one, develops critical reflective reasoning and life skills among students. VanLehn (1995) shared the adverse arguments, saying that nourishing of perceptive skills implied that the students must be able to make logical solutions to all those issues in tasks that require conceptual clarity. The prevailing situation of our educational system also requires such sudden changes in which students might nourish their perception skills and this may be possible only by introducing certain pedagogical changes in the whole system of teacher education, focusing more and more on motivation and autonomy for students to develop perceptive and critical thinking skills.

4. Research methodology.

To measure the usefulness of activity in ESL classroom, mixed- method (both quantitative & qualitative) access was used, and a well-tailored questionnaire was utilized for data collection. A semi-structured interview technique was used for qualitative data. A cross-sectional research design was used for this purpose. The researcher gathered data at a specific time by utilizing structured questionnaire and semi- structured interview as research device. The population consisted of Elementary School Teachers from Government schools. The sample consisted of 100 English Teachers. The researcher employed convenience sampling technique to collect data and opinions of 100 ESL professionals were observed employing Likert scale. The questionnaire included 21 items or statements to be answered by the respondents. To authenticate the reliability and internal coherence of the questionnaire, Cronbach’s alpha technique was used. Owing to the widespread Covid-19 pandemic around the world, all schools and colleges were closed, and due to unavailability of ESL teachers for face to face interaction on the topic, specially-tailored questionnaire was found reliable and more effective device for collecting data. Moreover, the respondents found it comparatively comfortable to provide their opinions on the propositions when eye-to-eye interviews were impossible and difficult to conduct during corona outbreak.

Formula:

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{k}{1-k} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \sigma_{yi}^2}{\sigma_x^2} \right)$$

Where “k” signifies total items on the scale.

$\sigma_{y_i}^2$ shows the variance related to item I σ_x^2 refers to deviation and fluctuation observed total scores.

5. Data Collection.

To get feedback on different statements related to the research topic, 100 ESL Teachers were selected for data collection. The respondents were Government Elementary Schools English teachers. The questionnaire was in the form of test items comprising 21 questions to be answered by respondents, which were further analyzed by making use of Likert scale. With the Cronbach's alpha of the measurement, the current self-administered scale reliability indicated a 0.789 which was reliable and valid for use. So, the accuracy of centralized flexibility for the 21 items in the questionnaire was very high so that the reasons could be detailed by focusing on each statement individually. For the purpose, the data got using the questionnaire further emphasized that the various causes for not utilizing the activities in ESL classrooms were substantially tested.

6. Data Analysis and Findings.

The feedback received from ESL teachers was analyzed using SPSS (24.0) to come to descriptive statistics to compute frequency counts, ratios and percentages. For a detailed discussion of the responses got by selected participants, descriptive statistics were shown. Similarly, tables showing frequency were displayed to show participants' responses for each valid statement in the questionnaire. Similarly, results were revealed in graphical form to make comparison of the possible reasons. This technique is considered the most effective-cum-reliable measure to map out reliability and inter-dependence of the items within the test (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). In this connection, Patrick McGraw Kline (1994) argues that the reliability estimates if the test bears any measurement error, and the same is applied to correlation of the test itself. Moreover, the value for Cronbach's alpha was found 0.789 which was adequate for the test items to be valid. Then, Mean (M) and Standard Deviation (SD) of the valid statements were found by Likert Scale to test each item. The detail of findings is as under:

Descriptive Analysis.

6.1 Gender- wise distribution of the sample.

Table 1. Detail of gender-wise distribution of sample.

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	66	66.0	66.0	66.0
	Female	34	34.0	34.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 2. Demographic features of the sample.

Table 1 and graph in figure 2 above depicted that the researcher collected data from 100 participants comprised of both male and females. Out of 100 participants, 66 were males while 34 were females. The difference was not in opinion among males and females. They both faced the issues and agreed upon the existing problems and lack of resources.

6.2 Age-wise description of the sample (respondents).

Table 2. Age-wise description of the sample (respondents).

Age					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-30	7	7.0	7.0	7.0
	31-40	25	25.0	25.0	32.0
	41-50	51	51.0	51.0	83.0
	51-60	17	17.0	17.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 3. Detail of age of participants in graphic form.

The age of participants showed in table 2 and figure 3 above revealed that the age range varied from 20-60 years of age. 7 participants were under 20-30 years of age, 25 under 31-40 years of age, 51 majority belonged to 41-50 years of age while only 17 were under 51-60 years of age. Analysis revealed that participants who were aged above 51 years responded to the statements quite differently, showing a discouraging attitude towards the implementation of activities in EFL classrooms to make the teaching more effective and productive. Whereas, the participants who were aged between 20 to 30 years showed a positive and encouraging attitude towards the utilization of activity in EFL classes. This revealed that young teachers were found comparatively more ready to bring a change in their teaching pedagogy and implementation of activities in EFL classes.

6.3 Academic qualification of the respondents.

Table 3. Academic qualification of the respondents.

		Academic Qualification			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	B.A	32	32.0	32.0	32.0
	M.A	60	60.0	60.0	92.0
	M. Phil	8	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4. Academic qualification of the respondents.

As for the qualification of the participants was concerned, table 3 above reveals that qualification of the respondents taking part in the research was minimum Bachelors and maximum M. Phil level. Majority, 60 out of 100 was Masters in the relevant subject, 32 participants did Bachelors, while 8 participants had completed M.Phil. M. Phil degree holder participants who participated in the data collection showed quite different results as compared to those with simple Bachelors qualification. The participants with higher qualification were found interested in using activities in EFL classroom during teaching in one way or the other, neglecting hurdles and making way through constraints, while the participants with only graduation showed less interest in using activities in the class, taking more into account the hurdles in their way for not using the activates in the class.

6.4 Professional qualification of the defendants.

Table 4. Professional qualification of the defendants.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	B.E.	68	68.0	68.0	68.0
	D				
	CT	8	8.0	8.0	76.0
	PTC	15	15.0	15.0	91.0
	M.E. D	9	9.0	9.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0		

Figure 5. Professional qualifications of the respondents.

The research revealed that the professional degree mattered a lot in affecting the results of the research, as professional degree holders showed quite a different approach towards the topic under discussion, as compared to those without professional degrees. Among 100 participants, 68 participants had completed Bachelors in Education (B.ED), 15 completed Primary Teaching Course (PTC), and 9 had done Masters in Education (M.Ed). While only 8 had done Certificate in Teaching (CT) as professional qualification, as shown in figure 5. The research revealed that the respondents who had done professional degree like B.Ed and M.Ed suggested that activity should be included in teaching methodology and it had a positive and productive result while the participants who had done PTC or without any professional qualification answered in negative and did not show any interest in using activity during teaching language.

6.5 Job Experience of the respondents.

Table 5. Job experience of the respondents (in years)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-5	10	10.0	10.0	10.0
	6-10	16	16.0	16.0	26.0
	11-15	13	13.0	13.0	39.0
	16-20	41	41.0	41.0	80.0
	21-25	17	17.0	17.0	97.0
	26 and above	3	3.0	3.0	100.0
Total		100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 6. Job experience of the respondents (in years)

The researcher found that the job experience also affected the results greatly. Table 5 above shows the Job experience of participants in years. Participants with different job experience gave different opinions on the topic under discussion. 41 participants were working from 16-20 years. 17 from 21-25 years, 16 were from 6-10 years and 13 from 11-15 years. While only 10 were working from 1-5 years and 3 participants were working since 26 and above years, as shown in figure 6 above. The research revealed that those participants who were young or newly appointed suggested that new techniques in teaching pedagogy should be used along with traditional ones and variations in curriculum and syllabus should be considered widely. Although they showed more interest and were found motivated, while the participants who were old in age suggested the modern techniques in a different manner and were found unwilling for curriculum changes in this modern era. So the difference of opinion and interest existed between old and young teachers on the basis of exposure and experience.

6.6 Econometric Analysis.

6.6.1 Scale: Reliability

Table 6. Case processing summary.

		N	%
Cases	Valid	100	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	100	100.0

a. List-wise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

6.6.2 Cronbach's alpha statistics.

Table 7. Cronbach's alpha statistics.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.789	25

Reliability of the scale was checked using Cronback alpha technique. Table 6 and 7 above indicate reliability of scale. It is considered that reliability and validity of scale should rely under 0.70 to 0.90. The current self administered scale reliability indicated a 0.789 and it means the scale was found quite reliable and valid for use.

6.6.3 Correlation Analysis.

Table 8. Correlation analysis.

		Correlations					EFL Teacher s Attitud es
		Lack of resour ces	Lack of training/fac ilities	Hurdles/Bar riers	Lack of motivation/Int erest		
Lack of resources	Pearson Correlation	1	.085	.617**	-.101	.190	
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.403	.000	.316	.058	
	N	100	100	100	100	100	
Lack of training/facilit ies	Pearson Correlation	.085	1	.130	.337**	.125	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.403		.196	.001	.214	
	N	100	100	100	100	100	
Hurdles/Barrie rs	Pearson Correlation	.617**	.130	1	-.188	-.028	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.196		.062	.782	
	N	100	100	100	100	100	
Lack of motivation/Int erest	Pearson Correlation	-.101	.337**	-.188	1	.142	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.316	.001	.062		.159	
	N	100	100	100	100	100	
EFL Teachers Attitudes	Pearson Correlation	.190	.125	-.028	.142	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.058	.214	.782	.159		
	N	100	100	100	100	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: author's own calculation based on survey data.

To measure the relationship between variables, the researcher applied correlation test. Table 8 above shows the details of results of correlation. There was a significant relation found between lack of resources and hurdles. Lack of training had a linkage with lack of motivation and interest (0.001**). The relationships were found significant and positive in magnitude. While other variables did not have any significant relation. It means one variable had a significant effect on the other one. They were found strongly interlinked with one another. If one was found affected, the other also was also affected. The relationship existed and profound to be positive in magnitude.

6.6.4 Regression analysis

Table 9. Regression analysis

Mode	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.309 ^a	.096	.058	1.29494

a. Predictors: (Constant), Lack of motivation/Interest, Lack of resources, Lack of training/facilities, Hurdles/Barriers

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	8.192	1.227		6.675	.000
	Lack of resources	.131	.049	.332	2.680	.009
	Lack of training/facilities	.077	.088	.092	.872	.385
	Hurdles/Barriers	-.155	.087	-.226	-	.079
	Lack of motivation/Interest	.037	.039	.102	1.774	.342

a. Dependent Variable: EFL Teachers Attitudes

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	16.858	4	4.214	2.513	.047 ^b
	Residual	159.302	95	1.677		
	Total	176.160	99			

a. Dependent Variable: EFL Teachers Attitudes

b. Predictors: (Constant), Lack of motivation/Interest, Lack of resources, Lack of training/facilities, Hurdles/Barriers

The regression analysis was applied to measure the impact of EFL teachers' attitudes on other independent variables. Results in table 9 above indicate that EFL teachers' attitudes did have an impact on lack of resources and hurdles or barriers they face ($r=0.000$). While it had no effect found among lack of training and lack of motivation. It means teachers attitudes changed with lack of resources and hurdles they faced during teaching. The obstacles might be the constraints of the syllabus, lack of teachers' interest and motivation, lack of professional qualifications, lack of English language skills and so on. If the teachers faced all of the above, their attitudes automatically changed. Teachers required resources and wanted to overcome these hurdles so they might perform better in their role and teach the learners.

6.6.5 T-Test (Group Statistics)

Table 10. Group Statistics.

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Lack of resources	Male	66	12.6364	3.06161	.37686
	Female	34	13.2059	3.92953	.67391
Lack of training/facilities	Male	66	9.4394	1.61844	.19922
	Female	34	9.4412	1.61791	.27747
Hurdles/Barriers	Male	66	12.4848	1.86665	.22977
	Female	34	12.9706	2.08145	.35697
Lack of motivation/Interest	Male	66	17.1818	3.41899	.42085
	Female	34	17.2059	4.14714	.71123
EFL Teachers Attitudes	Male	66	9.3182	1.34918	.16607
	Female	34	9.2059	1.32068	.22650

T-test was applied to measure the gender-specific differences among variables. It was found that there was no significant difference among variables. It was applied to see whether both male and female teachers faced the same issues or vice versa.

6.6.6 Independent Samples Test.

Table 11. Detail of tests of Independent Samples.

			Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
			F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2- tailed)	Mean Differ ence	Std. Error Differ ence	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
										Lower	Upper
Lack of resources	Equal variances assumed		2.242	.138	-.7	98	.427	-.5695	.71328	-1.98499	.84596
					54.17	.464	-.5695	.77212	-2.11742	.97838	
Lack of training/fa cilities	Equal variances assumed		.033	.857	-.05	98	.996	-.00178	.34162	-.67971	.67614
					66.78	.996	-.00178	.34158	-.68362	.68005	
Hurdles/B arriers	Equal variances assumed		1.373	.244	1.185	98	.239	-.48574	.40988	-1.29913	.32765
					60.71	.257	-.48574	.42452	-1.33470	.36322	
Lack of motivation /Interest	Equal variances assumed		.735	.393	-.031	98	.975	-.02406	.77691	-1.56582	1.51770
					56.63	.977	-.02406	.82641	-1.67916	1.63104	
EFL Teachers Attitudes	Equal variances assumed		.299	.586	-.397	98	.692	-.11230	.28280	-.44891	.67351
					68.03	.691	-.11230	.28086	-.44813	.67273	

Independent sample t-test was applied to measure the differences among variables on the basis of gender, as shown in table 11 above. No statistically significant difference was, however, found between variables on the basis of gender as is shown in table 11.

6.6.7 Chi-Square Test.

The chi-square analysis was applied to measure the association between variables. The results indicated a highly significant association among lack of resources, lack of training/facilities, hurdles/barriers the teachers face, lack of motivation with EFL teachers attitudes. If there is lack of resources, it was evident that there were no training facilities and opportunities, the hurdles and barriers also existed, lack of motivation and interest were faced by teachers. Moreover it affected the EFL teachers' attitudes. So chi-square was basically applied to measure the

link/association between all these variables. The association among all dependent and independent variables was found highly significant. It showing one variable affected the other one. Test statistics are shown in table 12 below:

Table 12. Test Statistics

	Lack of resources	Lack of training/facilities	Hurdles/Barriers	Lack of motivation/Interest	EFL Teachers Attitudes
Chi-Square	158.440 ^a	237.920 ^b	329.600 ^c	77.480 ^d	81.440 ^e
df	12	7	9	17	6
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 7.7.

b. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 12.5.

c. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 10.0.

d. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 5.6.

e. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 14.3.

6.7 Telephonic Survey Feedback of EFL Teachers.

Figure 7. Telephonic survey Feedback.

Telephonic survey of participants revealed that the highest percentage of participants (80 %) declared that teachers were not using activity during teaching due to lack of motivation, while 70 % of the participants claimed that they were not using the activity due to overcrowded classes and the same percentage revealed that tardiness on the part of teachers and lack of professional training from time to time were the main reasons for not utilizing activity in the language class. 60 % teachers responded that use of activity in the class was not possible due to lack of planning on the part of teachers also due to lack of required classroom for this purpose. 50 % responded that limited resources were also the cause of not using activity in the class. Only 30 % claimed that discipline was the major issue in crowded classes. The survey overall revealed that the major constraints faced by ESL teachers in government schools included tardiness, overcrowded classes and lack of lesson

planning on the part of the teachers. However, professional training was also revealed to be one of the reasons in this regard.

7. Discussion.

The real objective of conducting this study was to dig deep into the reasons as to why ESL teachers remain unable to use activities in their language class, and an attempt was made to observe and analyze deeply teachers' perceptions and opinions on this topic. Findings clearly throw light on the current prevailing constraints in the way of utilizing activities in the classroom. Findings reveal that, if certain deficiencies are positively met, activities can be utilized in elementary schools to get desired objectives. It can undoubtedly be said that a professionally trained teacher can plan so many different activities to implement in the language class. If the ESL teachers are left motivated to use this activity method, it can definitely yield potentially wonderful results along with saving much of teachers' time and, at the same time, minimizing the boredom usually left in traditional language classes. Once tailored, these activities can plenty of times be shared by different ESL teachers to be used in their own situations. A bulk of respondents with professional experience reveals that use of activity is very successful for language class for elementary level students. There are many activities available on teachers' end if they sincerely concentrate on the subject they are going to teach and plan their lessons well. The research throws light on how to overcome the constraints by putting their efforts to reconsider this method seriously and to switch over to this new mode of teaching. In this context, the respondents reveal that many of the constraints can simply be overcome if due attention is given to the reasons behind the causes. To start with, if activities are blended with subject matter and made a part of academic calendar, this method can easily be launched without anymore delay. Moreover, the respondents' opinions and proposition on the topic also show that no possible ranking was seen in the activities employed by ESL teachers during teaching, because if the activity is selected carefully and is well-tailored, may yield the same fruitful results for ESL teaching.

The results achieved from the study positively hold up the proposition that teaching English language by making an effective use of activity is not only indispensable to teach language to elementary students, but also the need of the hour to achieve desired outcome. The research reveals that there is only lack of motivation which is the most important point to focus, as shown in Fig. 7. The language teachers in government schools are still following the ages-old traditional method to teach language, and they have not welcomed the new method of teaching, nor do they exercise and entertain any method which makes use of activity, hence they feel no need and motivation to jump onto modern pedagogy. This may be due to several reasons, like, lack of motivation, lack of resources, lack of professional training, age factor and less time duration of the class. Tardiness on the part of the teachers and crowded classes are two other major factors revealed in the survey during interview. Comparatively observed, tardiness can be willingly overcome by teachers themselves if they consider professional ethics honestly, and realize or reconsider their duties well, while overcrowded classes, which is still an important issue in most of the government schools needs some remedial consideration. This too can be overcome by careful planning on the part of the language teacher if he or she makes some groups by dividing the whole class into different groups with group leaders and conduct activity each day engaging every group. Different innovative strategies can be made in this regard by the counseling and cooperation of the language teachers. Punjab Textbook Board (PTB) also appreciates and suggests teachers to use activity in the classroom. Each lesson is embedded with different activities to be followed at the end of each lesson.

The outcome also successfully focuses on the premise that lack of planning and lack of classroom may be the constraints in the way of usage of activity to teach language in the classroom. 60 % respondents as shown in Fig. 7 claimed that teachers do not plan their lessons beforehand and, thus, don't feel any need to utilize activity while teaching. This constraint can be overcome if the principal takes pains to address the staff members and teachers to complete their lesson plans including activities daily. Similarly, lack of classrooms, as some respondents complained, can also be overcome if the available rooms are exchanged with other classes and labs are also utilized off and on. One classroom should be spared for activity where rooms are fewer in number. The ideal situation is that the activity should be so designed as to be completed in the same classroom by making some room for the purpose. It will save time. There is no hurdle of resources in the class, as some of our practitioners in our government schools consider.

The results also disclose another important fact that the class duration for language class should be extended to meet the requirement suggested by the ESL teachers, as they require more time to teach lessons using activity. This problem can positively be solved if the language classes are conducted in the very first period which is comparatively longer than the rest ones because the incharge of the class has sufficient time for roll-call of the students and can spare some extra time for his lessons. Similarly, if the period just before break at noon may be utilized, the teacher may also find some extra time for language class, as there will be no more class till the break ends. Similarly, the first period just after the class can be spared for activity, as the students feel refreshed after break time and may tend to take more interest in activity then, leaving more fruitful and productive output. The research in hand also unveils the fact that science labs can also be utilized for this purpose, as they are more capacious than ordinary classrooms. Moreover, the help from other subject teachers

can also be sought to manage the activity well. It is better if the period for activity is included regularly in the timetable of the school to ensure maximum results, as many respondents declared that teachers don't bother to execute activity in their daily routine classes because there is no room for activity in the timetable.

Moreover, the results revealed that tardiness on the part of the language teachers counts much for their not using activity in the language class, as most of the teachers simply rely on the traditional approach to teach language and don't feel inclined to streamline their teaching methodology. The principal or coordinator in this concern should review the timetable and syllabus to ensure whether or not the activities have been included in the teaching methodology or not. He or she may pay surprise visits to classes to observe the practices going on in the class and this again may very well be overcome by holding meetings with the staff to discuss modern pedagogy in the class to teach language classes. Moreover, the services of the experts can be sought to deliver lectures on how to use activity in the class and how to embed activity in the syllabus contents or the lesson for effective and productive learning on the part of the learners.

8. Strengths and Limitations.

The present study has been carried out to achieve the desired objectives mentioned by the researcher in abstract. So, the findings of study are relevant to and compatible with the aims and objectives expected to be achieved in the abstract. The researcher has very keenly and justifiably chosen the tools for this research, by logically ensuring substantial data collection and opinions gathered from language professionals, both with the help of questionnaire and interview. Due consideration has been paid to formulating data collection questionnaire being well-tailored, factual and original, keeping in mind the sensitivity of the issue under probe and pilot testing has also been very carefully done to maximize the original finding for the study. Moreover, to avoid any ambiguity and irrelevancy, tables and graphs have been shown separately to enhance visual impact and cumulative comparison and clarity to show the reasons contributing to the problem. Furthermore, the citations mentioned in the literature review section are well justified and thoughtfully studied by the researcher.

Discussing the limitations observed in the present study, the arduous task has been accomplished during corona pandemic and e-mail and telephonic survey have been used to collect data. It was not possible for the researcher to visit and observe the classes directly because the whole country was under strict lockdown due to Covid-19, and due to absence of teachers in schools, telephonic survey was also found greatly helpful and useful tool for data collection. Added to this, the number of language teachers (sample) for data collection was relatively smaller due to prevalence of corona pandemic across the globe and non-availability of teachers due to large scale closure of educational institutions in Pakistan. However, to yield optimal results, the research could have opened further corridors in this area, detailing hitherto hidden issues related to the topic under discussion in a much broader context which could eventually have dug much deeper into the research question under debate.

9. Recommendations.

Taking into account the modern educational needs of the hour and modern pedagogical innovations, it is very much indispensable to bring a change in ages-old teaching technique and methods being used in ESL classrooms. It is all the more necessary to make the teaching-learning process a fun and creative process, resulting in developing students' language competency and academic excellence (Weimer, 2002). Teaching should be student centered, with full focus on achieving Students' Learning Outcomes SLOs. In this concern, teaching methodology matters a lot in achieving all these academic goals. The learning process should be made more creative, productive and fun, leaving no sign of boredom and monotony on the part of the learners. This may be possible if the teacher reconsiders the teaching method and revises his/her teaching technique and methods to streamline the learning demands, learning can be made more productive and result-oriented. So, by utilizing activities in teaching, students can be introduced with a totally new learning environment by utilizing all the possible modern technology and innovative skills. The use of activities during lessons in ESL class can make the learning warm, welcoming, and encouraging, with long-lasting impressions on students' minds. The study focuses on how the teachers can make their learning creative and productive, considering students' linguistic needs. If certain constraints are successfully met, which is possible as the respondents reveal, learning scenario can invariably be changed altogether. The learners should never be taken as empty vessels to be filled in with syllabus contents and students are generally expected to vomit out that specific knowledge when required. Rather they should be taken as creative thinkers. Students generally learn when they actually do by their own. They learn when they actually go through a process or activity, and they do remember that learning as a part of their individual experience, as Rillero (994) rightly points out when he asserts that learners learn only by putting themselves into that particular situation, just like a swimmer needs to enter into river for getting swimming experience.

So, the major responsibility rests mainly on the shoulders of ESL teachers who are to apply modern teaching methods to learning. Whichever method or technique they apply to make their teaching creative and effective, they should be motivated all the way to use activities to make teaching-learning easier and more productive. Moreover, certain changes in the timetable to accommodate activity - based learning and provision of some innovative and experienced ESL teachers at Elementary Level can bring a positive change in traditional pedagogy.

10. Concluding remarks.

The paper analyzed teachers' opinions and reservations on the constraints being faced by them in ESL classroom. It also focuses on how these constraints discourage teachers and stand as hurdle in their way of using activities during teaching. The paper observes the major factors that do not let the teachers use activity as a tool to make their teaching effective and productive and what are loopholes in the system and their current nature and status. More to this, the paper also paves way for overcoming some major constraints by offering different suggestions made by the researcher. The responses gathered from the respondents clearly reveal another important fact that majority of teachers are still following conventional method of teaching the English language and it is a pity that they are taking and treating English as a subject, and neglecting its importance as a language. They are not willing to consider the importance and need of modern teaching methodology to teach the English language, giving least importance to activity by offering different constraints in the way. However, it is a fact universally acknowledged that teacher's style and way of teaching attracts students' attention and leaves a long-lasting impression on students' memory. It not only motivates students to learn but also keeps the learners motivated and, in the long run, makes learning creative, natural and more result-oriented.

The present research also throws light on another important fact by highlighting psycholinguistic belief that the students gain information and knowledge by undergoing their own experiences and these experiences vary from learner to learner. Learning is something attained by real life experience. Students' actions and participation in some action or task make the learning productive in comparison with what we see in the conventional method of teaching which leaves the learners without any personal experiences to learn by doing, and paves way for making the teaching- learning experience rather boring.

Furthermore, the results suggest that, if certain constraints are removed and other barriers are successfully overcome, the use of activities in ESL classroom can make teaching easier, creative and long-lasting in the minds of learners. It may discourage the still-prevailing conventional methods, which are limited to writing rules of language by learners, cram them and reproduce when asked by teachers. By making effective use of available resources, the teachers may make the process of learning more productive, interesting, creative, encouraging and welcoming.

The research further paves way for researchers by providing new dimension to probe into the areas that have gone unaddressed so far, to check and observe the practicality and usage of activities at different academic levels in their own contexts by carefully considering students' linguistic and academic history. It may go a long way to find out the constraints in the way of utilizing activities to boost learning but will also provide teachers new dimensions to employ more innovative teaching techniques in future.

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